

CODEN [USA]: IAJPBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**A RESEARCH TO ASSESS ANTI-TUBERCULOSIS
TREATMENT (ATT) SIDE EFFECTS AMONG PATIENTS
SUFFERING FROM MOTOR-DOMINANT NEUROPATHY****¹Dr. Misbah Ijaz, ²Dr. Rehman Sarwar, ³Dr Ahsan Mahmood****¹Pmdc 93184-P, THQ Pattoki, Kasur, ²MO, Municipal Dispensary Thanewala Bazar, ³House Officer, Mayo Hospital Lahore.****Abstract**

Isoniazid is among effective treatments for TB (Tuberculosis) which can potently cause the severe onset of motor-dominant neuropathy that is also reversible with the supplementation of pyridoxine. In this research, we studied a female of forty-five years of age with an onset of psoas abscess and Mycobacterium tuberculosis culture positive at Sir Ganga Ram Hospital, Lahore (February to October 2017). The treatment of the patient started with antituberculous drugs that included a dose of isoniazid (5 mg/kg once a day). After three months severe weakness of the motor function was also evident in the patient especially in the lower limb including knee and ankle reflexes. The patient received Vit B-6 injection and treatment of isoniazid. After the treatment continuation, motor weakness improved gradually in the timeframe of a few months; whereas, sensory impairment remained persistent till two years. We need to be extra aware of the neurological effects caused by isoniazid especially in the individuals at risk for symptoms development and slow acetylator status is to be considered suspicious for such cases. Longer morbidity periods associated with an easily reversible state can possibly be controlled through an in-time initiation of Vit B-6 high dose therapies.

Keywords: *Neuropathy, Isoniazid, Vitamin B-6 (Vit B-6), Anti-Tuberculous Treatment (ATT), Pyridoxine and Therapy.*

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Please cite this article in press Misbah Ijaz et al., A Research To Assess Anti-Tuberculosis Treatment (Att) Side Effects Among Patients Suffering From Motor-Dominant Neuropathy., Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2018; 05(12).

INTRODUCTION:

In the grading of WHO, Pakistan stands at fifth position among TB affected countries as its population holds the large burden of tuberculosis. In Pakistan, an annual reporting of TB cases exceeds the count of 420,000 per year [1]. Among such cases, the majority of the TBN affected patients receive first-line anti-TB therapy known as INH (isonicotinyl hydrazine) or rifampicin, isoniazid, ethambutol, pyrazinamide and streptomycin. Isoniazid has an associated onset of sensory peripheral neuropathy that results in the form of numbness and burning of extremities. Some of the cases presenting sensory symptoms may show a rapid progress with related development of rapid motor weakness and rapid ataxia. Isoniazid also plays the role of competitive pyridoxine B-6 inhibitor and also activates the biological function which is less found for appropriate nerve cell functioning [2].

Isoniazid-induced neuropathy incidence is commonly very low which is in the range of (0.2% – 2%) among the general population [2]. This susceptibility is high among the elder population, in the course of pregnancy, malnourished, in chronic alcoholics, HIV (Human Immuno Deficiency Virus) cases and slow acetylator genotype patients [3]. Therefore, in the light of available guidelines, vitamin B-6 prophylaxis is good only for the patients who are at high risks [4 – 6].

In this research, our female middle-aged patient developed serious motor neuropathy and axonal sensory which lead to an onset of quadriparesis after three months of initiation of ATT management without an intake of Vit B-6 prophylaxis.

CASE REPORT:

In this research we studied a female of forty-five years of age with an onset of psoas abscess and Mycobacterium tuberculosis culture positive. Patient also complained difficulty while raising and sitting down on the chair with upper limb weakness. During initial treatment at a local hospital, our patient received ATT drugs such as isoniazid, rifampicin, pyrazinamide and ethambutol with a respective dose of 5 mg/kg, 10 mg/kg, 25 mg/kg & 15mg/kg for a period of two months. The treatment of the patient started with antituberculous drugs that included a dose of isoniazid (5 mg/kg once a day). After three months severe weakness of the motor function was also evident in the patient especially in the lower limb including knee and ankle reflexes. The patient received Vit B-6 injection and treatment of isoniazid. After the treatment continuation, motor weakness improved gradually in the timeframe of a few months; whereas, sensory impairment remained persistent till two years. Among co-morbidity

conditions the only available co-morbidity was hypertension and it was controlled through ACE (Angiotensin-Converting Enzyme) inhibitor lisinopril (10 mg). There was no history of diabetes, immunodeficiency, hepatic dysfunction, renal failure and HIV. The patient did not take any alcohol or smoke. She also denied for an onset of fever or upper respiratory tract infections. She was apparently recovering from TB as no fever sign was there and she also gained weight. When she came to the hospital, she was on a wheelchair because she was not capable enough to bear weight or walk with a stable BMI (26 kg/m²). General physical examination was not good; whereas, neurological examination showed sensorimotor tetra paresis along with the strength of the muscle as (4/5) among all the extremities. She also had reduced patellar tendon and Achilles reflexes with free peripheral joints. Touch sensation was also weak in the lower and upper limbs; whereas, cranial nerves were in better shape and intact. She also not complained for breathing difficulty or any sign of deglutition. She had symptoms of all four limbs with a deficiency of INH-induced Vit B-6 and differential GBS (Guillain Barre Syndrome). With the consent of neurologist, she started taking injections of Vit B-6.

As per the outcomes of clinical examination the level of haemoglobin was low (10.2 gm/dl); whereas other laboratory outcomes such as LDH (Lactate Dehydrogenase), ESR (Erythrocyte Sedimentation Rate), CPK (Creatine Phosphokinase), ALT liver enzymes and TSH (Thyroid Stimulating Hormone) were in the normal range.

Electromyography reflected that there was an onset of severe axonal sensorimotor polyneuropathy along with reduced bilateral peroneal motor nerves velocities conduction and supplying nerves to the muscle of right tibias anterior. As a result of outcomes analysis, the patient received the treatment of Vit B complex injection and amitriptyline gabapentin for the treatment of neuropathic pain. The patient also attended regular physiotherapy sessions. After one week there was a notable improvement in the standing ability at her own with the Vit B-6 initiation. On the follow-up visits, the overall physical ability was even better as the patient was able to walk and stand. The treatment was switched at a later stage to an oral dose of pyridoxine (100 mg in a day) with additional sessions of physiotherapy. Motor dysfunction also improved in the coming months but still mild limbs sensory deficit was persistent in the upper and lower limbs.

At the end of two years of treatment, she hardly managed to climb stairs with mild tingling and

numbness in the toes with power restoration of (5/5) among both lower and upper limbs.

DISCUSSION:

Numerous authors have disclosed the use of isoniazid as a causing agent of peripheral neuropathy in different series with a low range starting from 0.2% to 2% only [2, 3]. High risk patients possess an increased involvement for the neuropathy such patient present low acetylation status, HIV, chronic renal failure, diabetes, lactating women, malnourished, pregnant women, alcoholics, elder patients and all other using medicines with the effects of antagonize B-6 such as cycloserine, hydralazine, antiretroviral and penicillamine drugs [2, 3]. Therefore, the WHO guidelines recommend the high-risk patients with pyridoxine prophylaxis (10 mg – 25 mg) per day along with isoniazid in order to prevent an onset of neuropathy [4, 5]. Whereas, local Pakistani guidelines do not favour the use of prophylaxis B-6 in the patients at higher risks as those patients are highly endemic to such interventions [6]. Our patient was also a low-risk patient even then she developed serious motor dominant polyneuropathy which was reversed to pyridoxine supplementation at a later stage of disease management.

With an assumption of reduced low acetylator status as reported in the literature review, we decreased the amount of INH dose and completely resolved neuropathy with the help of supplementation of Vit B-6 [7]. Another patient also developed motor neuropathy after two weeks of IN therapy initiation which has an association to BMI status (18 kg/m²) [8].

Regional and local tuberculosis guidelines restrict the use of pyridoxine prophylaxis among patient presenting low-risk factors as the cost of the treatment increased 1500/- (PKR) in the time duration of six months. In addition to that, the reduced neuropathy incidence along with isoniazid use and its therapeutic pyridoxine dose reversibility is opposite to the common pyridoxine prescription as prophylaxis.

However, financial reasons bar the patients from regular follow-up and feedback process about the disease progress or control. General awareness is another issue among patients. Even in the better treatment routine of our patient, still, there were few residual deficiencies. Physicians need to be very much concerned and meticulous about the risk factors review for all patients undergoing ATT without the supplementation of pyridoxine. Physicians also need to educate their patients about the side effects of anti-

TB treatment so that the patients should also have a medical concern.

CONCLUSION:

The research outcomes highlight that INH neurological effects need proper attention especially in the patients presented with low-risk factors. Before the initiation of any ATT programme, the assessment of nutritional status is very much important. Moreover, it is also very much important that patients receiving ATT are to be educated and aware of the associated neurological risks and INH side-effects. A timely report about the neurological deficit will help in the control of reversible conditions and long-term morbidities.

REFERENCES:

1. National guidelines for the control of tuberculosis in Pakistan. [Online] 2015 [Cited 2015 March 19]. Available from: URL: <http://www.ntp.gov.pk/resource.php>.
2. Steichen O, Martinez Almoyna L, Brouker DT. Isoniazid-induced neuropathy: consider prevention. *Rev Mal Respir* 2006; 23: 157-60.
3. Zaoui A, Abdelghani A, Ben Salem H, Ouanes W. Early-onset severe isoniazid-induced motor dominant neuropathy: a case report. *Eastern Mediter Health J* 2012; 18:3.
4. Treatment of Tuberculosis. WHO Guidelines 4th Edition.2010. [Online] 2010 [Cited 2015 March 19]. Available from: URL: <http://www.int/publications/guidelines/tuberculosis/en>.
5. Eakarnanth A, Koomanachai P, Thamlikitkul V. Pyridoxine (VitaminB6) Usage in Tuberculosis Patients at Siri Raj Hospital. *Siri Raj Med J*2007; 59: 348-9
6. World Health Organization: The Global Plan to stop Tuberculosis report 2011-2015 [online] [cited 2015 March 19] Available from URL: <http://www.emro.who.int/pdf/pak/programmes/stoptuberculosis.pdf>.
7. Fekih L, Boussoffara L, Fenniche S, Abdelghaffar H, Megdiche ML. Neuropsychiatric side effects of anti-tuberculosis treatment. *Rev Med Liege* 2011; 66: 82-5.
8. Marks DJ, Dheda K, Dawson R, Ainslie G, Miller RF. Adverse events to anti-tuberculosis therapy: influence of HIV and antiretroviral drugs. *Int J STD AIDS* 2009; 20: 339-45.